

GRADATION IN PROFESSIONALLY FORMED PROVERBS

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ABSTRACT

The article is based on professions, which are based on proverbs on handicraft, carpentry, sewing, molding, ceramics, painting, and iron. In the family, first of all, the mother brings up her daughter. The first and most important things like the culture of attitudes and behavior daughter learns from her mother. For example, a person who works hard for the needs of others, cannot find time for doing his job: "Shoemaker's shoe is torn apart", the glue: "Weaver does not have a belt", A potter drinks water in a potter's pot".

Uzbek folk stories are characterized by exceptional abundance. It is the position of an ancestor who created it in the bottom of any article. That is why the proverbs do not argue, do not prove, but confirm or deny the accuracy, and all the opinions expressed by them are strict truths [2, 3]. It is difficult to find out when the folklore generated by extra linguistic foundations, but it is clear that they appear in ancient times, live in harmony with the people and reflect the lifestyle of that time. Their formation takes place on the basis of a particular image, which occurs on various occasions and on various socio-economic events. Occupation [a] is a type of field of expertise, a field of expertise; profession [4, 371], and in the Uzbek language there were occasions related to certain professions with certain conditions. Proverbs are divided into several types in this group, such as: People's proverbs those formed on the basis of on handicraft. Proverbs those formed on the

basis of carpentry People's proverbs formed on the basis of sewing. People's proverbs formed on the basis of weavery. People's proverbs formed on the basis of pottery. People's proverbs formed on the basis of dyery. People's proverbs formed based on blacksmithing, etc. People's proverbs formed which are based on handicraft. Handicraftsman.1) who is working with hands; 2) who is engaged in sewing shoes (ethics, etc.) [3, 399] Shoemaking is one of the most prominent traditions of the Uzbek people. For example: Shoemaker's shoe is torn. There are people who has a hard time trying to get people to do what they want, but they do not have time to do their job. Our people use this article in a figurative way. The master does not go to the knife, shoemaker to the owl. A craftsman works from early to late to create wealthy materials, to improve his or her own life, and of course, every craftsman uses a variety of work tools, depending on his or

her profession. At the same time, shoemakers often use their awls and carpenters use their saw-hand hoe and so on. Hence, shoemakers' labor tools frequently breaks down. Plasterer does not know the work of the patch. The patch- is a person who patch the shoes. [5, 482]. The plasterer - plaster the objects. [5, 80]. Because the patch is a master of his profession, he has mastered all aspects of his profession.

Naturally, the plasterer cannot perform the work of the patch as perfectly as he does. This is the correct meaning of the proverb. Allegoric meaning of this proverb means that everyone is perfectly mastered by his own profession and it is used in the sense that he cannot apparent himself in other spheres. People's proverbs formed on the basis of carpentry The carpenter [f-t] is a person whose job is to make or fix wooden objects or wooden parts of buildings. Carpentry - a name of profession [4, 240]. A board will rest untill an axe begins its work. This article explains with allegorical meanings in Hikmatnoma book: "A person can breathe in the tranquility of distressful times" [3, 61]. But in literature there is a point in the meaning of this article: "Let's have peace now, don't lose this moment": "It will rest until an ax begins||. With this kind of thinking Murad continued living in the house of rich [1, 144]. If the blade is sharp, it will cut the axe's handle People's proverbs formed on the basis of sewing. Sewing... is a name of occupation [5, 174] Uzbek people who are sewing skullcaps, suzane and dresses are named under the same name, and today this person specializes as a dressmaker: Where the needle moves, the rope goes in the same direction - when the guide starts (Whether it is the right way or the curb), the public

will go there. In the family's case the good or bad behavior of children is also dependent on the parental guidance [3, 150]. Everyone measure with their own length -As people's length and size are different, as well as their perception, intelligence, knowledge will be also different. When someone speaks as you would in your mind, someone tells you something meaningless or absurd. Therefore, it is not necessary to be sad "[3, 513]. People's proverbs formed on the basis of weaver. In the life of the Uzbek people formed different opinions on the basis of proverbs. For example, Aweawerhas not got a belt - as we know, every craftsman during his working period sells the best creations to the market. He uses the products that have not sold in the market, but does not miss out on the daily needs. As a result, the craftsman will not be able to buy the best of his products and use them for his own needs. See the selvage -take the weave, See the mother-take herdaughter. Option: Before taking your maid see -her mother, Before taking the weave see -border!

There are two selvages on the border of weave. If the selvage does not pull off and change, it will show that it is good quality. In the family, first of all, the mother brings up her daughter.

first and most important things like the culture of attitudes and behavior daughter learns from her mother. If the selvage should be kind, soft and with high quality, the girl is also should be educated, good-behaviour and must be ready for the future family. To atlas shirt - a weave patch - A person who is intelligent, beautiful, educated and so onin need of social development if she has a different outcome, and her spouse is not suit to her in such cases it is said in a hint manner. The

following meanings of this article: To copper pot - a muddy straw. To golden paper - a weave patch. To Amircon boot - a low shoe. To golden rings - a glass eye. People's proverbs formed on the basis of pottery. Pottery is a craftsman working in ceramic dishes. Pottery - a name of profession [4, 440]. A potter drinks water from a ceramic dish. During the course of their life, potteries put in the market for most of the pots made of pottery, and bottles in their place. This article, based on this vital truth, is used today in this and similar situations. This article has the following meanings: The potter does not have a bowl for drink. Look at the potter's trick: handing a ceramic dish. It does not make pottery - As we know that the pans and pitchers made by potters break down from time to time for some reason. It's known that a person's life is temporary, so it's going to end up in life. A fracture - potter's pitcher, A spilled - winemaker's wine. Winemaker is a person who is engaged in the preparation and sale of herbal drinks [4, 158]. This article says, "Yes, if it is broken the pitcher's pitcher and it has been spilled winemaker's wine. Would you be upset and angry? Do you feel sad and grief-stricken?! Do not worry about being sick, do not break your nerves, do not worry about it," [3, 371]. People's proverbs formed on the basis of dyer. Dyer - 1) a master, specialist, colorful artist of fabrics, yarn and others. 2) A master of home cleaning and painting technicians. Dyeing is a profession ... [4, 157]. Many people's proverbs have been created on the basis of

dye. Including: Painters' hand paint - The painters often have paint traces because they are painted, and this marks their paintwork. This is the correct meaning of the proverb.

Figurative meaning: It is used in the sense that a person is unable to perform any action, behavior such as his conduct and so on. The painter's paintwork dries, father's beards - it is used for the person who is cunning, foolish, slow and apathetic in order to hint him. People's proverbs formed on the basis of blacksmith. Blacksmith is a master who makes or repairs things made of iron. Blacksmithing - a name of profession [5, 159]. Beating hundreds of times of needle - once beating of blacksmith. This proverb is used when a person who has been working hard for a long time and is not doing well with a comparison of the another person who easily accomplishes the same thing. Weigh the iron is a must have - it means that every work must be done on time and only then this action can have a positive effect. The basis of the folk proverbs formed in the framework of professional curriculum usually consists of the products made by each profession, and the lifestyle events that occur in that profession. For example, a person who works hard for the needs of others, cannot find time for doing his job: "Shoemaker's shoe is torn apart", the glue: "Weaver does not have a belt", A potter drinks water in a potter's pot". Gradually, a proverb that has emerged from profession has its philosophy and has become commonplace.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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